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Education & Humanities

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All India Teacher Educators Association[®]

Vol. No. 4 (No. 6) April to September 2013

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Quality of Private “Teacher Education Colleges” in National Capital Region Delhi

Sanjeev Kumar Jha* Prof. Sohrab Ali**

Abstract

The research was an attempt to study the quality of Private Teacher Education colleges of Delhi NCR. The sample comprised of 6 principal, 30 Teacher Educator and 120 B.Ed. students. Colleges and Teacher Educators were selected with the purposive sampling and students were selected with simple random sampling technique. The sample was administered by three self developed tools i.e. 1. Interview Schedule for principals to study about admission criteria and Process, 2. Questionnaire for Faculty to study Teaching and Evaluation Methods/ Strategies and 3. Student's Satisfaction Scale to study student's satisfaction. The data statistically analyzed by mean and percentage. Result of the research are i) 50 percent marks in graduation is essential to take admission in B.Ed. followed by entrance examination for colleges affiliated to GGSIPU, Delhi and CCSU, Meerut by conductive by their respective University and in colleges affiliated to MDU Rohtak merit of marks of graduation or post graduation. ii) Lecturer method and Group Discussion Method are regularly used by 92 % and 86 % respectively of Teacher Educators for teaching and Observation method is used by 92 % of Teacher Educator for Evaluation. iii) Students are satisfied with Tangibility, Responsiveness and Assurance and not satisfied with Reliability and Empathy of these colleges.

Key Words: Quality, Tangibility, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy

Introduction

If the quality of school education is to improve then first step should be to improve the quality of teacher education. The colleges perform a critical role as an institutional agency for higher education. National Knowledge Commission (2009) “There must be focus on upgrading

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infrastructure (particularly enhance the ICT infrastructure), improving training of teachers, and continuous assessment of syllabi and examination.” So the emphasis is on teaching and training. Thus Teacher Education Colleges should be of high quality.

No authoritative definition of quality in higher Education is possible (Scott 1994). It is defined differently by different stakeholders “Product specification is actually the minimum conditions for quality, but not the sufficient condition”. The sufficient condition is customer satisfaction and beyond” (Mukhopadhyay, 2005). Quality is differently defined by parents, students, teachers, educational administrator and educationist differently. Quality is slippery term referred by Pfeffer J. & Coote 1991) so it is difficult to measure.

It is not surprising that parents, students, faculty members and employers understands the concept of quality with regard to higher education in different ways. Parents view quality as relating to input (e.g. ranking of the schools, reputations) output (e.g. Employability, academic placement) on the other hand, students saw quality as relating to the educational process (e.g. course and teaching) and outputs. Faculty members perceived quality as relating to the whole education system (e.g. input, process, and output). Employers saw quality as primarily related to the output (e.g. the skill set that the students bring to the workplace) Chua Clare (2004)

The present study considered a holistic approach to define the quality i.e. Input→Process→ Output.

Input means admission criteria and process adopted by the Private Education Colleges.

Process means teaching and evaluation methods used by Teachers Educators.

Output means satisfaction of the students studying in these colleges.

The Input→Process→Output gives the quality of Teachers Education colleges.

Rationale of the Study

Now-a-days Teacher Education Colleges are increasing exponentially throughout the nation. The participation of private players has a very significant role in such growth. But the experiences over the last few decades have clearly shown unlike school education, privatization has not led to any major improvements in the standards of higher education. Government colleges and universities have provided some better quality of teaching and infrastructure for higher education whereas private Teacher Education Colleges are providing their courses at minimum infrastructure and facilities. These private institutions of Teacher Education seem to have only money motive and it seems to have no vision to gave a quality Teacher Education.

One of the questions pertaining to privatization of the Teacher Education is as to whether private Teacher Education Colleges are really living up to the government/ society expectations. Although these Teacher Education Colleges do project themselves as top class institutions with reference to infrastructural facilities, faculties profile and teaching learning process apart from excellent placement services.

It is needed to look into the way these universities are functioning and quality of the Teacher Education Colleges and whether they are practically performing the assigned or projected task.

Objectives of the study

The following objectives are formulated to study in relation to Private Teacher Education Colleges of National Capital Region (NCR), Delhi

1. To study admission criteria and process adopted by the colleges i.e. Input
2. To study teaching and evaluation methods/ Strategies adopted by the Teacher Educators i.e. Process
3. To study the students satisfaction of the colleges i.e. Output

Research Questions of the study

- What are the Criteria and Process of admission adopted by the private colleges of teachers education of NCR i.e. Input.
- What are the Teaching and Evaluation Methods/ Strategies adopted by the Teacher Educators of private Teacher Education Colleges of NCR i.e. Process.

Hypotheses of the study

- Students satisfaction is low in private colleges of teachers education i.e. Output

Operational Definition of the terms used

1. **Admission criteria and Process:** Eligibility criteria and procedure that how the colleges take admission of the students.
2. **Student's satisfaction:** it is the perceived liking/feeling towards the service provided by their colleges.

Methodology of the Study

Method

Descriptive survey method was employed for the study.

Population and Sample of the study

Population

All the Teacher Education colleges running in National Capital Region having affiliation by Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University (GGSIPU) Delhi, *Chaudhary Charan Singh University (CCSU), Meerut (UP) and Maharshi Dayanand University (MDU), Rohtak (Haryana).*

Sample

The sample of the study was drawn from 2 colleges of each university (GGSIPU Delhi, CCSU Meerut, and MDU Rohtak). Colleges and Teacher Educators were selected with the purposive sampling and students were selected with simple random sampling technique.

Table 1.1:
Sample of the Study

Sr. No.	Colleges affiliated	GGIPU	CCSU	MDU	Total
1.	Principal	2	2	2	6
2.	Faculty	2x5=10	2x5=10	2x5=10	30
3.	Students	2x20=40	2x20=40	2x20=40	120

Tools Used

1. Interview Schedule for principals to study about admission criteria and Process: It has five questions related to admission Criteria and Process.
2. Questionnaire for Faculty to study Teaching and Evaluation Methods/ Strategies: It has two dimensions namely a) Teaching Methods/ Strategies and b) Evaluation Methods/ Strategies.
 - a) Teaching Methods/ Strategies: This section has eight commonly used teaching Methods/ Strategies at higher level
 - b) Evaluation Method/ Strategies: This section has seven commonly used evaluation Methods/ Strategies at higher level.

In this questionnaire teacher has to indicate how frequently s/he use the stated Methods/ Strategies i.e. Regularly, Sometimes, Rarely.

3. Student's Satisfaction Scale to study student's satisfaction: The tool is based on the Likert scale questions are ranging from five points, one to five (1-5), which is 1- strongly disagree, 2 - disagree, 3- neutral, 4- agree and 5- strongly agree. The questions instrument are taken from the SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al 1988), (Zeithml and Leonard Berry, 1988). It has five dimensions.
 - a. TANGIBILITY: the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and information material has six items.
 - b. RELIABILITY: the ability to perform the service accurately and dependably has two items,
 - c. RESPONSIVENESS - the willingness to help customers and provide a prompt service has three items,

- d. ASSURANCE: a combination of the Competence, Courtesy, and Credibility has four items and
- e. EMPATHY: a combination of the Access to physical and social, Communication Understanding the students seven items. So, the tool has total 22 items.

Statistical Techniques Used

The collected data statistically analyzed, with mean and percentage.

Analysis and Interpretation

Research Question 1: What are the Criteria and Process of admission adopted by the private colleges of teachers education of NCR i.e. Input.

All the Principals responded as “Private Teachers Education Colleges functioning in NCR are not enjoying the autonomy in relation to admission criteria and process”.

Admission Criteria:

All the Principals responded as “National Council of Teacher Education (NCTE) has laid norms regarding eligibility criteria i.e. candidates with at least fifty percent marks either in the Bachelor’s Degree and/or in the Master’s degree or any other qualification equivalent thereto, are eligible for admission to the programme. As well as the reservation in seats and relaxation in the qualifying marks in favour of the reserved categories shall be as per the rules of the concerned Government.” The norms laid by NCTE are mandatory to for Teacher’s Education Colleges/ Institute. So, the admission criteria for all the universities (i.e. GGSIU, CCSU, MDU which has mainly affiliated the private teacher education colleges in NCR) have a common criteria i.e. fifty percent marks in graduation or post graduation.

Process:

Principals of Private Teacher Education Colleges affiliated to GGSIPU, Delhi and CCSU, Meerut responded as “their affiliating university supply students through counselling based on the merit of entrance test conducted by the respective university” whereas Principals of Private Teacher Education Colleges affiliated to MDU, Rohtak responded as “their affiliating university supply students through counselling based on the merit of graduation or post graduation marks.

Research question 2: What are the Teaching and Evaluation Methods/ Strategies adopted by the Teacher Educators of private Teacher Education Colleges of NCR i.e. Process.

The table shows the percentage of teacher use the methods/ strategies with the frequencies namely regularly, sometime and rarely.

Table 1.2:
Teaching and Evaluation Methods/ Strategies

S. No.	Teaching Method/ Strategies	Regularly (% of Teachers Use)	Sometime (% of Teachers Use)	Rarely (% of Teachers Use)
1	Power Point	23%	48%	29%
2	Presentation Seminar	18%	69%	14%
3	Overhead Project transparency	28%	34%	49%
4	Case Study	0%	20%	81%
5	Field/ Industrial Visit	2%	25%	73%
6	Group Discussion	86%	8%	9%
7	Project	5%	12%	83%
8	Lecturer	92%	8%	0
Evaluation Method/ Strategies		(has 7 items but teachers responded on 4)		
1	Observation	89%	3%	9%
2	Weekly Test/Unit Test	12%	80%	90%
3	Monthly Test	15%	82%	4%
4	Assignment	7%	92%	2%

Lecture and Group Discussion Methods (Table 1.2) are used regularly by 92% and 86% of Teacher Educators. Shahida Sajjad (2010) found that most of the students rated lecture method as the best teaching method and group discussion was rated as the second best method at higher level so methods are as per students need whereas observation is used for evaluation by majority of the Teacher Educators.

Hypotheses 1: Students satisfaction is low in private colleges of teachers education i.e. Output

- i. **TANGIBILITY:** The mean gap score between perception and expectation is approximately one so students are satisfied with infrastructure of their colleges,
- ii. **RELIABILITY:** The mean gap score between perception and expectation is more than 3.5 so reliability of these colleges is not up to the mark. Students are not satisfied with reliability.
- iii. **RESPONSIVENESS:** the mean gap score between perception and expectation is 0.5 so students feel the teaching and non teaching staffs is responsive. Students are satisfied with responsiveness of their college's staff.

- iv. ASSURANCE: the mean gap score between perception and expectation is one (approximately) so students are satisfied with the assurance of their colleges.
- v. EMPATHY: the mean gap score between perception and expectation is 2.3 so the students feel their colleges have the physical resources but they don't have access to these and their problems are not understood by colleges administrator. So the students are not satisfied with empathy of their Colleges.

Conclusion

All the colleges have to follow the criteria of 50% marks in graduation. Entrance test or marks of graduation or post graduation becomes the basis for merit. Lecture and Group Discussion methods are used regularly by most of the teacher educators, the methods rate first and second by the students of higher education found by Shahida Sajjad (2010) so the teaching methods are as per students. Observation is regularly used by teacher educators. Students are satisfied with tangibility, responsiveness and assurance of the colleges whereas unsatisfied with reliability and empathy. It shows that colleges have maintained the infrastructure but access to them is limited that is why unsatisfied with empathy along with it teachers are not able to use innovative teaching methods more frequently.

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All India Teacher Educators Association®

(Registered Under Societies Registration Act 1860)
[Regn. No.194 of 2007-2008, Rohtak (Haryana)]

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Printed & Published by:

GLOBAL BOOKS ORGANISATION
(Publisher & Distributor)

Office : Saraswati House, U-9 Subhash Park,
Solanki Road, Uttam Nagar, New Delhi-110059
Ph: 011-25335169, 9899071610, 9899071490, 9899521610
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